

Eliciting The Acoustic Properties Of Tone In Esan Language Using PRAAT

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ABSTRACT

This study reviews the acoustic properties of tone in Esan language which are suitable for discriminating the age and gender of native speakers. Esan is a tonal language. The lexical and grammatical meaning of words can be affected by tone. Speech recording were elicited from four (4) native Esan speakers for the purpose of analysis. Some properties reviewed include fundamental frequency (f₀), intensity, formant, and duration. It was observed that these acoustic properties were suitable for discriminating between the ages and gender of Esan speakers.

Keywords: Esan, Tone, fundamental frequency, f₀, intensity, formant, duration

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1. INTRODUCTION

Sound can be described as a potentially audible disturbance of a medium produced by a vibrating source (Kiss, 2009). It is a mechanical oscillation with wave-like propagation through air, liquids or solid bodies (Heutschi, 2016). The perceptual capabilities of the human ear according to Heutschi (2016) are in three different frequency ranges: the normal hearing range (16 Hz - 16 kHz), the lower frequencies (infra-sound) and the higher frequencies (ultra-sound). Acoustics is the science that studies the production, control, transmission, reception, and effects of sound (Heutschi, 2016; Kiss, 2009). The goal of acoustics is to quantify and describe the properties of sounds with the help of various wave-related models (Kiss, 2009). The waveform gives a pictorial view of how amplitude varies over time. Acoustics seek to understand how sound is generated, propagated, perceived by humans, as well as how it interacts with matter.

Acoustic features can be used to describe sound properties of a tonal language. Ekpenyong et al (2008) identified some problems in the area of tone representation for African tone languages such as “terracing problems, words in context, homographs, loan words/personal names, numbers, dates and abbreviations”. Despite the problems in tone representation, significant meanings can still be derived from the sound’s acoustic features as well as the tone of the spoken word. Word classes, to an extent, could be distinguished by its tone pattern (Urua, 2001).

1.1 Tone Language

Tone is a phonological category that distinguishes words or utterances (Hartmann, 2007). It refers to pitch differences perceived as variations of the fundamental frequency (f_0). Pitch varies in speech, depending on the sex, age, height or emotional state of the speaker. Pitch can be influenced by consonants and it is a notable factor in determining the realisation of tones (Urua, et al., 2003). It is the relative value of pitch within a word or phrasal contour that determines the phonological category of tone, and not the absolute pitch value.

A language that uses tone to differentiate word meanings is called a *tone* language. Tone can be used to differentiate lexical and grammatical meanings. Tones are associated with the vowels and syllabic consonants. The lexical function of tone distinguishes the meaning of words by their tone. A significant advantage of intonational features is it’s resistant to noise and transmission distortions (Ekpenyong, et al., 2011). Basically, tone languages have two levels namely a High(H) and a Low(L) tone. However, many tone languages also have a Mid tone (M), and may even possess more distinctive level tones (Udoh, 2003; Hartmann, 2007). The levels can combine to produce *Contour tones* like ‘Rising and Falling’ (Udoh, 2003; Hartmann, 2007). Rising tones combine a Low(L) and a High(H) tone (LH), and falling tones combine a High(H) and a Low(L) tone (HL) as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1: A speech sample showing tones

1.2 Esan Language

Esan is a tonal language spoken by natives from the Esan Central, Esan West, Egor, Esan North-East, Esan South-East and Igueben Local Government Areas, in Edo state, Nigeria. It is the sixth largest native language spoken in Nigeria. The language is tonal, for example, in Esan *úmè* means ‘salt’, whereas *úmé* also means ‘you are good’. It can be observed that the major difference in the two words is the tone. This difference in tone gives rise to a different meaning. Esan language is dominated with high tones. Most Esan words commence with high tones irrespective of the emotional state of the speaker. Esan, being a tonal language, has its pitch carrying phonological information which can be detected by observing rising, falling, or otherwise marked pitch contours. Although pitch features alone are insufficient to distinguish all the phonemes of a language, pitch (absolute height or contour) can be the most distinguishing feature between two sounds (Metze, et al., 2013).

Esan is said to be a member of the North Central branch of Edoid (NCE) and is grouped with Edo, Ora - Emai - Iuleha, Yekhee, Uneme and Ghotuo as Proto North Central Edoid (PNCE) (Ejele, 1994). The phonetic consonants and vowels are shown in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Esan Phonetic Consonant Chart. (Ejele, 1994)

Place	bilabial	labio- dental	alveolar	alveopalatal	Palatal	velar	labio- velar	glottal
plosive	p b		t d			k g	kp gb	h
fricative	β	f v	s z	ʃ		x ɣ		
affricate				tʃ dʒ				
nasal	m		n					
lateral			l					
trill			r					
glide					j		w	

Table 2: Phonemic vowel chart of Esan (Ejele, 1994)

Place	front/nasal	central/nasal	back/nasal
Manner			
high	i ĩ		u ũ
mid	e		o
halfmid	ɛ ẽ		ɔ ɔ̃
low		a ă	

Ejele (2016) stated the following facts about the Esan language:

- i. Esan has thirty-two (32) letters of the alphabet made up of twenty-five(25) consonants and seven(7) vowels. For the phonetic consonant and phonemic vowel charts of Esan see Table 1 and 2.
- ii. Esan has five nasal vowels spelt as- in, ɛn, an, ɔn, un- which contrast with their oral counterparts i, e, ɛ, a, ɔ, o, u. Esan does not normally have /e,o/ as nasal vowels.
- iii. All vowels are spelt with a following letter ‘n’ after the nasal consonant /m/.
- iv. Words are spelt in full form, irrespective of how they are pronounced, so no more use of hyphen to represent elisions. This takes care of word boundary modification involving elision eg. ‘gbe uzo’ and ‘gbuzo’.
- v. That to improve the efficiency of Esan writing system, it was approved that words be tone-marked where its absence would lead to ambiguity. Otherwise, only the high tone should be tone marked.

2. STATEMENT OF PROBLEM

A speech, as a spoken word, carries so much information. Besides understanding what the speaker is talking about, we can also know more about the speaker. A speech can be analysed to identify specific information about the speaker such as the age, gender, height, emotion and so on. The challenge is identifying and extracting the features that are relevant to the required information. This study demonstrates how to identify and extract relevant acoustic properties that can be used to identify vital information in a tonal language. Esan language was used as a case study.

3. OBJECTIVE

The objective of this study is to demonstrate how the acoustic properties of a tonal language can be elicited.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Participants

We recorded four (4) Esan speakers; two(2) males and two(2) females. One male and one female fall within the age range of 65 – 80years, while the other respondents fall within the ages of 25 – 40 years. All are native Esan speakers.

4.2 Mode of corpus elicitation

An Android Smartphone was used to elicit the sound recordings. By default, sound recordings are in .3gpp file format. However, this file format is not suitable for our analysis. Hence, the original files were converted to a .wav file format. Furthermore, we used Audacity software as a tool of choice to convert the original stereo mode to a mono sound mode. The edited sound file is then uploaded unto Praat for analysis. A text grid file is created for annotations alongside the sound file. The text grid files from annotations can generate the label (.lab) files (Ekpenyong, et al, 2008).

To investigate the acoustic properties of tone in Esan, we used the sentence below and each recording was analysed using Praat.

English: Today is a day of joy!
Esan: ẹ̀dẹ̀ nẹ̀ ẹ̀lẹ̀nà eghoḡho nọ

Praat is an Open source software tool used to elicit specific information from a sound file.

5. ANALYSIS AND RESULT

The acoustic properties analysed are formant, f_0 , duration and Intensity.

5.1 Formant

Formants are properties that reflect the position of vowels. Often F1 and F2 are used for speech analysis. Figures 2-5 show the formants; the lines indicate F1, F2, F3, and F4 from down upwards. When the spectrogram is observed closely, it is noted that the lines indicating formants F1 and F2 are better defined than that of F3 and F4. Notably, the data from F1 and F2 were more reliable for the analysis.

Fig. 2: Spectrogram showing formant for 1st Male Speaker

Fig. 3: Spectrogram showing formant for 2nd Male Speaker

Fig. 4: Spectrogram showing formant for 1st Female Speaker

Fig. 5: Spectrogram showing formant for 2nd Female Speaker

5.2 Fundamental Frequency (f0)

Urua (2001) notes that labelling and taking F0 measurements requires that the auditory and visual observation of the speech wave forms, spectrograms and pitch tracings should be synchronised. Figure 6 gives an outlook of the f0 features of four native Esan Speakers.

Fig. 6: Chart showing f0 for the various speakers

In Figure 6 we observed that the younger female speaker has a significantly higher pitch at some point. The chart shows that the female genders have a fairly consistently higher f0 than the males. Also, it was observed that both female speakers had a significantly higher average f0. In Table 3 the average f0 result shows that the younger speakers produced a higher average f0 than their older counterpart.

Table 3: Average f0 for the speakers

S/N	GENDER	AGE RANGE	Average F0
1.	Male	65 - 80years	131.2245179
2.	Female	65 - 80years	213.2205241
3.	Female	25 - 40years	214.6387685
4.	Male	25 - 40years	174.0636741

5.3 Duration

The duration is a measure of the total time a particular speech was made. Different individuals produce speech sounds at varying length of time. This property can be used to distinguish between speakers or the emotional state of a particular speaker.

Table 4: Duration for the speakers

S/N	GENDER	AGE RANGE	Duration
1.	Male	65 - 80years	1.689secs
2.	Female	65 - 80years	2.360secs
3.	Female	25 - 40years	2.376secs
4.	Male	25 - 40years	2.296secs

Table 4 highlights the approximate duration for each of the native Esan speakers as shown in Figures 2-5. From available data, the males demonstrated their ability to speak within a shorter duration (1.689secs and 2.296secs). When compared closely, it is noted that the older speakers tend to complete a statement in a shorter time frame. For example, the younger male speaker had duration of 2.296secs as against 1.689secs of the older male. Similarly, the younger female had duration of 2.376secs while the older female completed her statement in 2.360secs.

5.4 Intensity

Sound intensity describes the energy transport related to a sound wave. It indicates the amount of sound energy per unit time or sound power that passes through an orthogonal unit area. The sound intensity is a vector and points in the same direction as the sound particle velocity (Heutschi, 2016). The intensity of the sensation of a sound is described by its loudness. In the power spectrum, intensity is viewed as the overall heights of the peaks as seen in Figures 2-5.

Fig. 7: Chart showing the intensity of speech

The intensity of sound made by the Esan speakers showed some closeness. However, sharp variations occurred for the female speakers as seen in Figure 7. This was evident where there was a pause in the sentence. We can agree, from the data, that the male gender had a shorter pause time when making a speech.

On the average, we notice that the older male spoke loudest. This could possibly indicate the degree of masculinity. However, the younger female had a slightly higher average intensity than her younger male counterpart as seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Average Intensity of speech

S/N	GENDER	AGE RANGE	Average Intensity (dB)
1.	Male	65 - 80years	72.12557849
2.	Female	65 - 80years	62.15442146
3.	Female	25 - 40years	65.84607685
4.	Male	25 - 40years	64.90039014

Fig. 8: Bar chart showing the average intensity

Figure 8 shows the bar chart of the average intensity for the Esan speakers under review. The male and female within the age range of 25-40 spoke almost as loud as each other. However, there is a very significant difference in the older male and female. There is also a great difference in the intensity of both males. This suggests therefore, that intensity may be a suitable acoustic property to discriminate gender of different age groups in tone languages.

6 CONCLUSION

This study reviews the acoustic properties of tone in Esan. We obtained a corpus of four(4) native speakers of different age groups. It was demonstrated that acoustic properties such as formant, f_0 , duration, and Intensity carries vital information about the speakers. Esan, as a tone language, are indicated with High (H), Low (L) and Coutour tones which differentiates lexical and grammatical meanings. The study does not exhaust all the acoustic properties of tone. Further research can consider the usefulness or otherwise of formants F3 and F4 in tonal languages.

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